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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FLOATING
TABLETS OF RANITIDINE HYDROCHLORIDE****E. Satheesh Kumar* and Venkatesh Kyavars**

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Article Received: May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

The present study is carried out with an aim to prepare and evaluate the floating tablets of Ranitidine Hydrochloride. The floating tablets were based on effervescent approach using sodium bicarbonate a gas generating agent. The FTIR studies show that there is no incompatibility between polymers and excipients used in the formulation. The tablets were prepared by Direct compression method. The effect of polymers such as HPMC K4M, Chitosan, Guar gum and Carbopol 934 on drug release profile was evaluated. The effect of HPMC K4M, Chitosan, Guar gum & Carbopol 934 on floating properties were also investigated. The result of In vitro dissolution study showed that the drug release profile could be controlled by increasing the concentration of HPMC and Chitosan. The formulation containing HPMC K4M and Chitosan showed 85.42±0.42 drug release at the end of 8 hours. Hence, Floating drug delivery system of Ranitidine Hydrochloride is prepared to increase the bioavailability of the drug and prolonged therapeutic effect.

Keywords: Floating drug delivery system, HPMC, Chitosan, Ranitidine Hydrochloride, Controlled release.

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INTRODUCTION:

The advancement to perpetuate dosage form in the stomach for enhancing retention time have been made which includes floating [1], swelling and expanding [2,3], bioadhesive [4,5], high density [6] and modified shape systems [7,8]. Out of which, floating and bioadhesive systems are using most commonly.

Floating drug delivery system:

Floating systems or Hydro dynamically balanced systems are low-density systems that have sufficient buoyancy to float over the gastric contents and remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time. After release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach. This results in an increased gastric residence time (GRT) and a better control of the fluctuations in plasma drug concentration. However, besides a minimal gastric content needed to allow the proper achievement of the buoyancy retention principle, a minimal level of floating force (F) is also required to keep the dosage form reliably buoyant on the surface of the meal. Many buoyant systems have been developed based on granules, powders, capsules, tablets, laminated films and hollow microsphere.

Formulation of this device must comply with the following criteria

- 1) It must have sufficient structure to form a cohesive gel barrier.
- 2) It must maintain an overall specific gravity lower than that of gastric contents (1.004-1.010).
- 3) It should dissolve slowly enough to serve as a drug reservoir[9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Chemicals and reagents:**

Ranitidine hydrochloride and Chitosan was provided as a gift sample by Heterolab, Hyderabad, India. Sodium bicarbonate and Guar Gum was supplied by Nice chemicals Pvt Ltd Kochi-682024, Kerala, India. HPMC K4M was supplied by Research-lab fine industries, Mumbai 400002. Carbopol 934 was supplied by Moly chem. Mumbai. Talc, Magnesium Stearate and Microcrystalline cellulose was supplied by Sd fine-chem-limited, Mumbai, India.

DRUG POLYMER COMPATIBILITY STUDIES:**FTIR studies:**

A physical mixture containing pure drug and pure polymers with ratio of 1:1 was transferred into a screw capped bottle and stored at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ RH 65% for a period of 1 month. After the study period, the samples were subjected for FTIR analysis. The study was performed on Fourier transformer infrared spectrophotometer Bruker. The samples (drug, polymers and physical mixtures) were prepared on KBr disks. The samples were scanned over wave number range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Spectra were analyzed for drug polymer interactions and functional groups identification.

Construction of calibration curve:

Accurately weighed quantity of drug (100 mg) was dissolved in 0.1N HCl solution in 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to 100 ml. From this stock solution 1ml is withdrawn from the volumetric flask and volume is made up to 100 ml with 0.1N HCl solution. From this 2nd stock solution (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), 2 ml, 4 ml, 6 ml, 8 ml and 10ml is withdrawn and made to 10 ml to give the concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solutions respectively. The absorbance of these solutions were determined in the UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 322 nm and calibration curve was plotted.

Table 1: Data for calibration curve of Ranitidine Hydrochloride

S.No	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	2	0.014 \pm 0.002
3	4	0.031 \pm 0.003
4	6	0.046 \pm 0.002
5	8	0.060 \pm 0.001
6	10	0.075 \pm 0.003
	Regression	0.999
	Slope	0.007

Figure 1: Calibration curve of Ranitidine Hydrochloride

EVALUATION STUDIES:

MICROMERITIC PROPERTIES [10]:

Angle of Repose (θ):

The frictional forces in a loose powder or granules can be measured by the angle of repose. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of powder or granules and the horizontal plane.

Bulk Density:

An amount of powder equivalent to 10 g was accurately weighed, placed in a 100 ml measuring cylinder without compaction. The volume occupied was measured and the initial bulk density was calculated.

Tapped density:

Tapped density (TD) of a powder is the ratio of the mass of the powder to the volume occupied by the powder after a fixed number of taps. The tapped density of the powder represents its random dense packing. An amount of powder equivalent to 10 g was accurately weighed, transferred into a 100 ml measuring cylinder and 500 taps were tapped. The

final volume was recorded and the tapped density was calculated.

Compressibility Index:

Compressibility index of powder mix was determined by Carr's compressibility index calculated by following formula.

$$\text{Carr's index}(\%) = \frac{\text{TD} - \text{BD}}{\text{TD}} \times 100$$

Where,

BD = Bulk Density

TD = Tapped Density

Hausner's ratio:

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by the following formula

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{t}{d}$$

Where 't' is the tapped density and 'd' is bulk density. Lower H (<1.25) indicates better flow properties than higher ones (>1.25).

Table 2: Standard values as per I.P

S. No	Flow properties	Angle of repose(θ)	Compressibility Index (%)	Hausner's ratio
1	Excellent	25-30	<10	1.00-1.11
2	Good	31-35	11-15	1.12-1.18
3	Fair	36-40	16-20	1.19-1.25
4	Passable	41-45	21-25	1.26-1.34
5	Poor	46-55	26-31	1.35-1.45
6	Very poor	56-65	32-37	1.46-1.59
7	Very very poor	> 66	>38	>1.6

PREPARATION OF THE TABLET FORMULATION BY DIRECT COMPRESSION METHOD

Each tablet weight 450 mg containing Ranitidine Hydrochloride, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) K4M, Guar gum, Chitosan, Carbopal, Sodium bicarbonate, Citric acid, Microcrystalline cellulose, Magnesium stearate and Talc were prepared by direct compression method. The Ranitidine hydrochloride, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) K4M, Guar gum, Chitosan, Carbopol934, Sodium bicarbonate, Citric acid, Microcrystalline cellulose are passed through the sieve No. 85. All the ingredients are mixed well for 15 min in the mortar and again mixed with lubricant for 3 min in a mortar. The mixture was compressed by using 5 mm concave punches of BB tooling on eight station rotary tablet compression machine.

Table 3: General composition of formulation prepared by Direct compression method

INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Ranitidine HCL	150mg							
HPMC K4M	50mg	-	50mg	-	50mg	-	100mg	100mg
Carbopol 934	100mg	-	-	50mg	-	50mg	50mg	-
Chitosan	-	50mg	100mg	-	-	100mg	-	-
Guargum	-	100mg	-	100mg	100mg	-	-	50mg
Sodium bicarbonate	50mg							
Citric acid	25mg							
Microcrystalline cellulose	65mg							
Magnesium stearate	5mg							
Talc	5mg							
Total wt of tablet (mg)	450mg							

EVALUATION OF TABLETS**Weight variation test:**

The weight of the tablet is routinely determined to confirm that a tablet contains the proper amount of the drug. The test is done by weighing 20 tablets individually. Calculate the average weight and comparing the individual weight to the average. The tablets ought to meet the IP specifications that not more than 2 tablets are outside the percentage limits and no tablet differs by more than 2 times the percentage limit. An IP official limit of percentage deviation of tablet is presented in the table.

Table 4: Limits for Tablet Weight variation test

Average weight of tablet (mg)	Maximum % Difference allowed
80 or less	±10 %
From 80 to 250	±7.5 %
> 250	±5 %

Thickness:

The thickness in millimeters (mm) was measured individually for 3 pre-weighed tablets by using Vernier callipers (Arvind Engineering co., Hyderabad). The average thickness and standard deviation were calculated.

Hardness:

Hardness, which is now more appropriately called crushing strength determinations are made during tablet production and are used to determine the need for pressure adjustment on tablet machine. If the tablet is too hard, it may not disintegrate in the required period of time to meet the dissolution

specifications. If it is too soft, it may not be able to withstand the handling during subsequent processing such as coating or packaging and shipping operations. The force required to break the tablet is measured in kilograms. The small and portable hardness tester measures the force required to break the tablet when the force generated by a coil spring is applied diametrically to the tablet.

Friability:

Friction and shock are the forces that most often cause tablets to chip, cap or break. The friability test is closely related to tablet hardness and designed to evaluate the ability of the tablet to withstand abrasion in packaging, handling and shipping. It is usually measured by the use of the Roche Friabilator.

Method:

A number of tablets are weighed and placed in the apparatus where they are exposed to rolling and repeated shocks as they fall 6 inches in each turn within the apparatus. After four minutes of this treatment or 100 revolutions, the tablets are weighed and the weight compared with the initial weight. The loss due to abrasion is a measure of the tablet friability. The value is expressed as a percentage. A maximum weight loss of not more than 1% of the weight of the tablets being tested during the friability test is considered generally acceptable and any broken or smashed tablets are not picked.

The percentage friability was determined by the formula:

$$\% \text{ Friability} = (W1 - W2) / W1 \times 100$$

W1 = Weight of tablets before test
W2 = Weight of tablets after test

Swelling index:

The studies were carried out gravimetrically. Swelling media used for these studies were distilled water and simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2). The prepared tablets were introduced into the swelling media. At predetermined time intervals the tablets were removed from medium, excess water was blotted with tissue paper and immediately weighed. This procedure was repeated until the tablet reached constant weight. The swelling index was calculated using following formula.

$$\text{Swelling Index} = \frac{W_b - W_a}{W_a} \times 100$$

Where, W_a = Weight of dry tablet, W_b = Weight of swollen tablet

FLOATING PROPERTIES OF TABLETS

The *In vitro* buoyancy was determined by floating lag time. The tablets were placed in a 100 ml glass beaker containing 0.1 N HCl.

Floating Lag Time:

The time required for the tablet to rise to the surface of the medium and float was determined as floating lag time.

Floating Duration Time:

The time for which the tablet remained floating on the surface of medium was determined as floating duration time.

IN VITRO DISSOLUTION METHODOLOGY:

In-vitro drug release study was performed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using eight station USP type-II apparatus with paddle rotating at 50 rpm. The drug release study was carried out in 0.1N HCl by taking about 900 ml of the dissolution medium. The drug release study was performed in 0.1N HCl to demonstrate the availability of Ranitidine Hydrochloride. About 5 ml of sample was withdrawn at specified time intervals from the dissolution medium and replaced with equal volume of fresh medium. Samples were filtered through whatmann filter paper and analyzed using UV spectrophotometer (T60, PG Instruments) at 322.0nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

LIST OF MICROMERITIC PROPERTIES OF BLENDS

The angle of repose was found to be in the range of 21.36° to 39.8° , which indicate excellent to passable flow properties of the powder mixture. The Carr's index was found to be in the range of 4 to 20, which indicates excellent to good compressibility of the powder mixture. Hausner's ratio was found in the range of 1.07 to 1.20, which indicates good flow properties as reported in the below table.

Table 5: Determination of flow properties of powder

Code	Bulk density g/cm^3	Tapped density g/cm^3	Angle of repose (θ)	Carr's index %	Hausner's ratio
F1	0.292 ± 0.021	0.459 ± 0.020	30.04 ± 0.12	36.35 ± 0.14	1.57
F2	0.438 ± 0.011	0.496 ± 0.025	27.98 ± 0.02	11.69 ± 0.21	1.13
F3	0.449 ± 0.015	0.461 ± 0.023	29.36 ± 0.04	29.95 ± 0.04	1.42
F4	0.315 ± 0.022	0.556 ± 0.013	30.38 ± 0.41	44.24 ± 0.41	1.76
F5	0.410 ± 0.028	0.726 ± 0.032	28.97 ± 0.01	43.44 ± 0.23	1.76
F6	0.404 ± 0.030	0.669 ± 0.038	29.55 ± 0.23	39.56 ± 0.21	1.65
F7	0.409 ± 0.034	0.621 ± 0.040	30.86 ± 0.22	34.08 ± 0.12	1.51
F8	0.446 ± 0.039	0.720 ± 0.039	27.15 ± 0.15	38.12 ± 0.23	1.61

The bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio were observed and reveals that all formulations blend has good flow characteristics and flow rate than the raw material.

RESULTS OF DRUG-EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDIES - FTIR

Figure 2: FTIR of Ranitidine Pure drug

Figure 3: FTIR of Ranitidine + HPMC K4M

Figure 4: FTIR of Ranitidine + Guar gum

Figure 5: FTIR of Ranitidine + Carbopol

Figure 6: FTIR of Ranitidine + Chitosan

Figure 7: FTIR of Ranitidine + Sodium bicarbonate

Figure 8: FTIR of Ranitidine + Citric acid

Figure 9: FTIR of Ranitidine + Magnesium stearate

Figure 10: FTIR of Ranitidine + Talc

Figure 11: FTIR of Ranitidine + Microcrystalline cellulose

EVALUATIONS OF THE PREPARED TABLETS FOR PHYSICAL PARAMETERS:

All formulations were tested for Physical parameters like Hardness, Thickness, Weight Variation and Friability found to be within the Pharmacopoeial limits. The results of the tests were reported in the below table. The drug content of all the formulations was determined and was found to be within the permissible limit. This study indicated that all the prepared formulations were good.

Table 6: List of Physical parameters

Formulation code	Hardness (kg/cm ³)	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)
F1	5±0.5	455±0.477	2.9±0.2	0.86
F2	3±0.3	447±0.469	2.7±0.1	1.35
F3	2±0.2	454±0.477	2.8±0.2	0.82
F4	3±0.5	445±0.467	2.9±0.1	0
F5	2±0.2	421±0.442	2.8±0.1	1.2
F6	3±0.6	446±0.468	2.8±0.2	0
F7	4±0.4	448±0.470	2.9±0.2	0
F8	2±0.3	447±0.469	2.8±0.2	0.884

Floating properties and swelling properties:

All formulations were tested for floating properties like floating lag time, total floating time, swelling properties and results were reported in the below table. Tablets of all formulations had floating lag time below 15 minutes regardless of viscosity and content of HPMC, because of evolution of CO₂ resulting from the interaction between sodium bicarbonate and dissolution medium and entrapment of gas inside the hydrated polymeric matrices enables the dosage form to float by lowering the density of the matrices.

Table 7: Results of the floating properties & swelling properties

Formulation	Floating Lag Time	Floating Time	Swelling index (%)
F1	Fails to Float	22 hours	42.10±0.21
F2	Fails to Float	8 hours	40.78±0.42
F3	4 min	22 hours	167.3±0.33
F4	Fails to Float	2 hours 13 min	137.2±0.23
F5	14 sec	4 hours	125.5±0.54
F6	Fails to Float	-	79.06±0.82
F7	Fails to Float	-	65.21±0.66
F8	45 sec	4 hours	52.27±0.57

In-Vitro Dissolution Studies**Table 8: In-vitro dissolution study of Formulations (F1-F4) in 0.1N HCl**

S.No	Time(hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.5	2.113±0.012	22.61±0.12	39.44±0.32	3.05±0.02
3	1	3.678±0.022	29.37±0.23	46.64±0.54	4.38±0.22
4	2	5.713±0.014	32.63±0.18	55.41±0.66	5.00±0.35
5	3	13.46±0.15	37.25±0.22	62.53±0.22	5.87±0.44
6	4	15.65±0.08	40.22±0.52	65.43±0.82	12.78±0.42
7	5	17.84±0.18	53.76±0.63	68.64±0.63	26.44±0.65
8	6	25.42±0.16	56.68±0.46	69.97±0.54	48.99±0.82
9	7	38.84±0.15	65.84±0.33	72.39±0.46	68.44±0.46
10	8	50.40±0.22	73.18±0.24	85.42±0.42	74.82±0.82

Figure 12: In-vitro drug release data of all the formulations [F1-F4]

Table 9: In-vitro dissolution study of Formulations (F5-F8) in 0.1N HCl

S.No	Time(hrs)	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.5	45.53±0.42	47.89±0.35	1.80±0.11	49.46±0.32
3	1	58.46±0.52	48.99±0.44	2.66±0.23	58.46±0.55
4	2	65.58±0.66	49.46±0.65	4.69±0.42	66.91±0.68
5	3	76.85±0.73	49.77±0.45	23.60±0.62	69.11±0.63
6	4	82.26±0.66	50.40±0.64	32.63±0.83	71.84±0.83
7	5	85.42±0.52	68.64±0.48	40.22±0.73	74.05±0.84
8	6	92.52±0.43	75.15±0.63	52.5±0.82	82.26±0.86
9	7	96.47±0.53	82.26±0.55	65.58±0.83	88.57±0.62
10	8	98.05±0.66	84.63±0.63	76.73±0.63	95.68±0.54

Figure 13: In-vitro drug release data of all the formulations [F5-F8]**Dissolution:**

Dissolution studies revealed that all the formulations from F1-F8 were in the range of 50.40±0.22% to 98.05±0.66%. Among all formulations F3 was shown less drug release in 8hrs that is 85.42±0.42%, Out of which F3 was found to be optimized formulation by observing all the parameters and as it has less drug release in 8 hrs that is 85.42±0.42%.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

1. Systematic studies were conducted by using four different polymers in different concentrations to prepare Ranitidine Hydrochloride floating tablets by direct compression method. All the prepared systems were evaluated for the different properties.
2. By performing FTIR studies, no interaction was confirmed. Formulated tablets gave satisfactory results for various evaluation parameters like tablet hardness, friability, weight variation and thickness.
3. Floating lag time was found to be in the range of 45 Sec to 4 min and F3 was found to be 4 min.

4. Floating duration time was found to be in the range of 4 to 22 hrs and F3 was found to be 22 hrs.
5. *In-vitro* drug release was carried out by using 0.1 N HCl. Formulation F1 containing HPMC K4M and Carbopol934 showed drug release of 50.40±0.22% up to 8 hrs, but the drug release from the formulation F2 containing Chitosan and guar gum shows 73.18±0.24% in 8 hrs.
6. Formulation F3 containing HPMC K4M and Chitosan showed 85.42±0.42% but in formulation F4 containing Carbopol 934 and Guar gum was observed that the drug release was 74.82±0.82% in 8 hrs.
7. Formulation F5 containing HPMC K4M and Guar gum showed drug release of 98.05±0.66% but the formulation F6 containing Carbopol 934 and Chitosan showed 84.63±0.63% drug release within 8 hrs.
8. Formulation F7 containing HPMC K4M and Carbopol934 showed 76.73±0.63% but in formulation F8 containing HPMC K4M and Guar gum observed that the drug release was 95.68±0.54% in 8 hrs.

Floating drug delivery system of Ranitidine Hydrochloride is prepared to increase the bioavailability of the drug by direct compression method using polymers like Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) K4M, Carbopol934, Chitosan, Sodium bicarbonate, Microcrystalline cellulose, Citric acid, Magnesium stearate. From the results obtained it can be concluded that among all the formulations with HPMC K4M and Chitosan, showed control release. Hence, Floating drug delivery system of Ranitidine Hydrochloride is prepared to increase the bioavailability of the drug and prolonged therapeutic effect.

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